

A Framework for ADAS Testing: Integrated Simulation System with Hardware-in-the-Loop Testing (Appendices)

This document contains the appendices of a paper with the above title. The paper proposes a novel testing framework intended for testing ADAS functionalities. The proposed framework aims to tackle the deficiencies observed in existing testing frameworks, including poor performance in simulating adverse weather conditions, complexity and cost from using multiple Radar Target Emulators (RTE) to simulate targets larger than 32, or inability to emulate full scene radar simulation. The proposed framework is currently undergoing testing within an industrial context. The appendices contain the results of completed component tests, along with additional framework details that were not included in the paper due to space constraints.

The structure of this file is organized as follows: Section 1 presents the outcomes of the evaluation through reviews, including the assessment of two EuroNCAP scenarios, the examination of camera and radar parameters, and the evaluation of weather condition simulations. Section 2 presents the evaluations carried out to assess the turning table actuation.

1. Validation by Review and Visualization

NCAP (New Car Assessment Programme) test scenarios are carefully designed to mirror real-world collision situations, serving to assess a vehicle's capacity to safeguard its occupants in the event of a crash. The NCAP framework provides standardized results from crash tests, facilitating comparisons that determine the safety ratings of various vehicles. The incorporation of NCAP scenarios into a simulation framework offers the advantage of early-stage software testing during the development process. This early-stage testing is invaluable for manufacturers and suppliers, providing insights into system performance and prompting appropriate actions as needed.

To ensure the conformity of NCAP test scenarios implemented within the simulation framework with EuroNCAP specifications, a process of validation is imperative. A comprehensive validation can be achieved by executing the test cases on a Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL) setup. However, it's important to note that the integration of the framework with the HiL system was still in progress. Consequently, the validation of the implemented NCAP test scenarios is carried out through a review of the developed test cases. Additionally, the verification of adverse weather conditions is executed by examining the visual outputs generated by the CARLA simulator. This process ensures that the simulated conditions accurately replicate real-world climatic challenges. The evaluation involved team members from our industry partner, including two individuals with ten years of expertise in virtual testing and another team member who possesses four years of experience in HiL system modeling.

The selection of subjects for these reviews was based on their expertise in the field. We sought individuals with experience in virtual ADAS testing and a strong background in framework development. The reviews were conducted individually, with one-on-one meetings. We had prepared a set of questions that they were required to address as part of their assessment of the framework. We ensured that they had a comprehensive understanding of the framework before starting the review of the test cases and other aspects. The review sessions typically lasted for one hour, which included walking through the steps to execute scenarios within CARLA.

In the rest of this section, the results of evaluations conducted by reviews are presented.

1.1. Assessing Two EuroNCAP Scenarios

The CPNA (Car to Pedestrian Nearside Adult) and CPFA (Car to Pedestrian Farside Adult) scenarios are depicted in Figure 1 and Figure 2, respectively. In the CPNA scenario, the pedestrian's speed (V_p) is 5 km/h, while in the CPFA scenario, it is 8 km/h. Vehicle speed (V_v) ranges from 10 km/h to 60 km/h in both CPNA and CPFA scenarios. The precise starting point for the pedestrian's movement, ensuring the impact point (P_i) aligns with the center of the lane, is determined through distance calculations (d) [1].

Table 1 presents the test cases, which were subjected to a thorough review by three subjects. Test parameters, including vehicle speed (V_v), pedestrian speed (V_p), and distance (d), were meticulously cross-referenced with the EuroNCAP protocol and visualized within the CARLA simulator. The reviewers addressed the following inquiries by comparing the test parameters in CARLA with those specified in the EuroNCAP protocol:

- Is the vehicle velocity in CARLA consistent throughout the CPNA and CPFA scenarios? All three respondents confirmed that the vehicle velocity remains constant in both scenarios.
- What is the vehicle velocity range in CARLA for CPNA and CPFA? All three respondents noted a velocity range of 10-60 km/h for both scenarios, confirming its alignment with the EuroNCAP protocol.
- What are the pedestrian speeds in CARLA for CPNA and CPFA? The three respondents confirmed a pedestrian speed of 5 km/h for CPNA and 8 km/h for CPFA.
- What is the distance between the pedestrian and the point of impact (P_i) in CARLA for CPFA and CPNA scenarios? The three respondents attested to the allocation of 4m for CPNA and 6m for CPFA.
- Do all the above results conform to the official EuroNCAP protocol? The respondents confirmed that all test parameter values comply with the EuroNCAP protocol.

Figure 1. CPNA scenario [1]

Figure 2: CPFA scenario [1]

Table 1: Parameters for Scenario Testing

Scenarios	V_v (km/h)	V_p (km/h)	d (metres)	score _{max}
CPNA	10	5	8	1
	20		16	1
	30		24	2
	40		32	3
	50		40	2
	60		48	1
CPFA	10	8	7.5	1
	20		15	1
	30		22.5	2
	40		30	3
	50		37.5	2
	60		45	1

1.2. Assessment of Radar and Camera Sensor Parametrization

To ensure the accuracy and dependability of test results, the creation of a digital twin for sensors within a simulation framework is imperative. This digital twin is constructed within the CARLA simulator by porting the real sensor's specifications, a process known as parametrization. The authenticity of the simulation framework is guaranteed by verifying that the parameters of the virtual sensors align with those of their real-world counterparts. Furthermore, the simulation developed here is designed to be versatile and can replicate a wide range of RADAR and camera sensors. Table 2 provides an overview of the parameters configured for the camera sensor within this research.

Table 2: Camera Parameters

Parameters	Type	Default	Description
image_size_x	int	800	Image width in pixels.
image_size_y	int	600	Image height in pixels.
fov	float	109.0	Horizontal field of view in degrees.
sensor_tick	float	0.0	Simulation seconds between sensor captures (ticks).

Table 3 provides a comprehensive view of the radar sensor parameters that have been parametrized in this research. To confirm their accuracy in replicating real-world sensors, these parameters have been reviewed by subjects.

Table 3: Radar Parameters

Parameters	Type	Value	Description
Range	float	250m	Maximum distance to measure/raycast in meters.
Horizontal fov	float	60°	Horizontal field of view in degrees.
Vertical fov	float	9°	Vertical field of view in degrees.
Cycle Time/ sensor_tick	float	60ms	Simulation seconds between sensor captures (ticks).
points per second	int	1500	Points generated by all lasers per second.

The review process involves a comparison of the specifications between the real sensors and their digital counterparts. The outcomes of the review confirm that the digital twin sensors have been accurately parametrized.

1.3. Evaluation of Weather Conditions by Visualization

To assess the resilience of ADAS functionalities, the simulation framework must accommodate various adverse weather conditions, including sunny, rainy, foggy, nighttime, and combinations thereof. These climatic variations significantly impact sensors like radar, cameras, and GNSS. Evaluating the robustness of sensor fusion algorithms involves subjecting the test vehicle to such adverse weather conditions. For example, in foggy conditions, cameras may struggle to detect all objects within their field of view. In such scenarios, sensor data from radar can be integrated with camera data to identify obstacles in the vehicle's path. A summary of the weather conditions and their impact on affected sensors is provided in Table 4, where symbols like (x) indicate the affected sensors and (–) denote those unaffected.

Table 4: Effects on sensors

Sensors	Precipitation	Fog	Night
GNSS	x	-	-
Camera	x	x	x
Radar	x	x	-
Gyro	-	-	-

The accuracy of the weather simulations is confirmed by visualizing them using the CARLA simulator, as depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Weather Simulations

2. Evaluation of Turning Table Actuation

Yaw refers to the rotation of the vehicle around its vertical axis, which can be influenced by multiple factors including steering inputs, road conditions, and wind. Yaw simulation is a valuable tool for assessing a vehicle's stability in situations involving oversteer and understeer. It calculates the current yaw angle of the vehicle, thereby serving as a test for the path planning algorithm. When combined with simulated GNSS data, yaw simulation can be used to test the localization of the vehicle under examination.

Therefore, yaw simulation is an important aspect of the proposed framework and is verified in two stages. The initial stage ensures data integrity between CARLA and Arduino, the latter being responsible for actuating the turning table. In the second stage, verification is performed by comparing the yaw angle provided by CARLA with the current angular position of the turning table after actuation.

Figure 4 presents the results of the data integrity test. The blue graph represents the yaw angle from CARLA, while the orange graph signifies the data retrieved from Arduino. Both graphs clearly indicate that the angle transmitted by CARLA aligns precisely with the data received by Arduino. Figure 5 provides insight into the turning table's direction of rotation in relation to its angular position, which underlies the direction information presented in Figure 4. A counterclockwise rotation of the turning table signifies a left turn, while a clockwise rotation indicates a right turn.

Figure 4. Results of data integrity test

Figure 5. Direction of rotation

Since the turning table lacks feedback mechanisms to determine its current angular position, there is no scientifically rigorous method to verify its actuation. Consequently, the sole approach to verify the actuation is through visual observation of the mechanical rotation of the turning table. To ensure the precision of turning table actuation, evaluation was conducted via testing and peer reviews. These tests involved sending various degrees of rotation commands through CARLA and comparing the observed rotation degrees on the turning table.

To reinforce the reliability of these tests, they were conducted and reviewed with the participation of two industrial partners. One subject possesses a ten-year background in virtual testing, while the other has four years of expertise in HiL system modeling. To enhance clarity, we have included a video in this appendix, demonstrating the turning table actuation in conjunction with CARLA car yawing. It's worth noting that the turning table exhibits a deviation of $\pm 0.33^\circ$ for a complete 360° rotation, as identified during the setup benchmarking in [2]. This margin of error may accumulate over multiple consecutive runs. Therefore, while the gyroscope simulation integrated within this framework serves to test overall functionality, for precise angular measurements, it is advisable to conduct tests on an actual vehicle.

3. Cross Verification of GNSS and Yaw Simulation

This section encompasses the additional parts of the conducted evaluation that were omitted from the paper due to space constraints.

GNSS spoofing was initially statically evaluated through the emulation of GNSS coordinates from CARLA on a smartphone. Figure 6 depicts two images. The image on the left is from a smartphone, while the one on the right is from the CARLA simulator. In the CARLA simulator, a vehicle is spawned at a precise GNSS coordinate, and the same coordinates are emulated on the smartphone (highlighted by red boxes in the figure).

Figure 6. GNSS spoofing visualization

Figure 7 illustrates dynamic GNSS spoofing, where the coordinates are updated as the vehicle moves within the CARLA simulator. This can be observed through changes in the speedometer and the arrow sign on Google Maps, indicating the vehicle's movement.

Figure 7. Dynamic GNSS spoofing

References

- [1] Rodrigo Gutiérrez, J. Felipe Arango, Carlos Gomez-Huélamo, Luis M. Bergasa, Rafael Barea and Javier Araluce, "Validation Method of a Self-Driving Architecture for Unexpected Pedestrian Scenario in CARLA Simulator," IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV), 2021, pp. 1144-1149.
- [2] Fabian Kristmann, "Entwicklung einer modularen Fahrtrichtungssimulation durch die Rotation eines Steuergerätes mit einem Gyrosensor an HiL-Prüfständen," Bertrand Technik GmbH, 2022, pp. 1-120.